

Benchmarking of Serpent2/OFFBEAT and Cardinal for Coupling Neutron Transport and Thermo-Mechanics of an eVinci-like Microreactor

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ABSTRACT

The solid-state nature of heat-pipe-cooled microreactors requires the development of high-fidelity multiphysics simulation tools capable of accurately capturing the coupling between neutron transport with thermo-mechanical behavior. In this work, a preliminary benchmarking study is conducted to compare such capabilities of the Serpent2/OFFBEAT workflow and Cardinal. Both methodologies rely on high-resolution Monte Carlo neutron transport simulations performed on an unstructured mesh representing a unit cell of an eVinci-like microreactor. The resulting spatially dependent power density is subsequently transferred to the corresponding thermo-mechanical solvers to compute the temperature and displacement distributions under steady-state operating conditions. Eigenvalue calculations can then be repeated on the same unstructured mesh to quantify reactivity feedback. The temperature feedback contribution is obtained by imposing the computed temperature distribution on a cell-by-cell basis, whereas the thermal expansion feedback is assessed by deforming the mesh and updating material densities to ensure mass conservation. This study presents a benchmarking analysis of both standalone Monte Carlo neutronics codes and thermal-mechanical solvers, as well as their coupling. The primary objective is to quantify and separate the discrepancies arising from intrinsic differences between the codes from those introduced by the coupling methodologies themselves. The results also establish the foundation for a fully coupled benchmark that integrates the thermo-mechanical behavior with the neutron transport of the system.

Keywords: Benchmark, Cardinal, OFFBEAT, Serpent2, eVinci

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the nuclear community has shown growing interest in the development of microreactors. These systems are more compact than conventional nuclear reactors and are designed to deliver a thermal power up to several tens of megawatts. Their designs emphasize inherent safety and reliability, aiming to minimize the human intervention required to ensure their correct operation. They can be manufactured and assembled in controlled factory environments and are small enough to be easily transported. All these features make microreactors very well-suited for deployment in remote or hard-to-reach areas, for military and space applications, and decentralized energy markets [1].

Among the various designs under development, Heat-Pipe-Cooled Microreactors (HPMs) represent one of the most mature concepts, largely due to the Kilopower project that culminated with the successful demonstration of the KRUSTY experiment [2]. Their inherent safety largely derives from the use of heat pipes as the primary cooling system. In fact, heat pipes function by transferring heat through the phase change of their working fluid, enabling a passive, self-regulating heat removal mechanism within operational limits. Furthermore, the working fluid circulates via natural capillary action, rather

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than relying on mechanical pumps, which enhances both reliability and safety. Another key feature of HPMs lies in their solid-state configuration. Their design consists of a solid block made from different materials depending on its function — such as moderators, fuel, or stainless steel for providing structural support. The block presents channels for hosting heat pipes and, depending on the design, also fuel or moderator rods.

The solid-state nature of HPMs necessitates the development of simulation tools that couple thermo-mechanics with neutronics. Such tools would have the potential to accurately predict sources of reactivity feedback, as well as assess the thermo-mechanical behavior of core components under neutron irradiation damage. To achieve high-fidelity results, these models must meet the following requirements: the capability to simulate neutron transport on unstructured meshes; the inclusion of models that predict heat transfer across gaps as dimensional changes occur; the ability to account for multi-body mechanical interactions; and a consistent framework for mapping fields from the neutronics code to the thermo-mechanical solver.

A study proposing a coupling methodology that features such requirements were presented by Genoni et al. [3], where Serpent2 and the OFFBEAT OpenFOAM-based fuel performance code were coupled to quantify the reactivity feedback associated with the thermal expansion of an eVinci-like core. This work presents a preliminary benchmark between the Serpent2/OFFBEAT framework and Cardinal to evaluate the temperature-reactivity feedback of an eVinci-like core. The analysis is carried out on a single unit cell (i.e., in this context, a single 3D graphite block including fuel and heat pipes) and compares the results obtained from standalone Monte Carlo neutronics calculations, standalone thermal simulations, and coupled thermal–neutronic runs. The aim is to establish a foundation for future benchmarks that will incorporate the full thermo-mechanical–neutronic coupling of the system.

2. MATERIALS & TOOLS

The benchmarking is conducted between Serpent2/OFFBEAT and Cardinal, a MOOSE application that couples OpenMC with any MOOSE physics module. It is essential to note that some discrepancies in the results may arise from fundamental differences in the codes, a factor that must be taken into account when interpreting them. The following sections provide a concise comparison between the two tool-chains, highlighting key differences in both the thermo-mechanical solvers and the neutron transport Monte Carlo codes. Finally, the coupling methodologies utilized by Serpent2/OFFBEAT and Cardinal will be discussed.

2.1. OFFBEAT and MOOSE

The primary distinction between the thermo-mechanics solvers lies in their discretization methods. OFFBEAT [4] is an open-source nuclear fuel performance code built on the OpenFOAM C++ library, which employs the Finite Volume Method (FVM) to solve partial differential equations (PDEs). While at its core is a thermo-mechanical solver, OFFBEAT also incorporates models to simulate nuclear fuel behavior. In contrast, MOOSE [5] is an open source multiphysics framework that uses the Finite Element Method (FEM), an approach for solving PDEs traditionally favored for thermo-mechanical simulations. Although the MOOSE thermo-mechanics module does not include typical nuclear fuel performance models, these are available in BISON. At the time of this analysis, the author did not have access to a BISON license. However, this was not a major limitation, as the simulation does not involve any burn-up dependent material behavior.

Both OFFBEAT and MOOSE incorporate models for updating the gap heat transfer coefficient as deformation progresses, eliminating the need for explicit meshing of the gap region. The gap heat-transfer coefficient is evaluated as a summation of multiple contributions. The first term, associated with gas conduction, is calculated as the ratio of gas thermal conductivity to gap thickness. The thermal conductivity of the gas is expressed as a function of the average gap temperature; however, OFFBEAT ad-

ditionally accounts for variations in the gas composition when evaluating this parameter. The second term represents the radiative contribution, expressed as a function of surface emissivity and temperatures. Finally, OFFBEAT includes an additional contact thermal resistance term that develops only when mechanical contact occurs—a contribution not included in MOOSE. These code differences did not introduce inconsistencies in the benchmarking, since the simulations assumed a constant gas composition and no occurrence of mechanical contact. The latter assumption was also necessary since both in Monte Carlo codes, overlapping might lead to erroneous results. For the Serpen2/OFFBEAT workflow, a workaround exists by using the implicit gap contact model, which stitches the meshes together during contact instead of allowing overlapping.

2.2. Serpent2 and OpenMC

Serpent2 [6] and OpenMC [7] are Monte Carlo-based codes designed to simulate coupled neutron-gamma transport. One of the most significant differences between them lies in their neutron tracking algorithms: Serpent2 uses delta tracking or a combination of delta-tracking and surface-tracking, while OpenMC is currently limited to surface tracking.

Delta tracking is particularly well-suited for Monte Carlo simulations involving geometries with a large number of cells, such as unstructured meshes where each cell is assigned a different temperature. This method avoids the computational overhead of calculating the distance to the nearest surface within a cell every time a collision occurs, which is required in surface tracking. As a result, delta tracking can significantly reduce the computational cost of the simulation, with the limitation of allowing collision-based rather than flux-based tallies, which tend to yield higher statistical uncertainty when evaluating reaction rates and might require more particle histories to be simulated. The surface tracking routine in OpenMC is instead not ideal for tallying within individual mesh cells. To address this limitation, the MOAB skinner is used by Cardinal to dynamically bin the spatial domain into multiple cells based on the temperature distribution calculated by MOOSE. This process is guided by user-defined parameters such as the temperature range where to apply the skinning, minimum and maximum temperatures, and the number of temperature bins.

Both codes enable temperature-dependent physics by generating Doppler-broadened cross-sections on the fly, allowing cross-section data to be stored for a single reference temperature instead of every temperature point required in the model. Such a capability is particularly valuable for simulations with numerous temperature-defined regions, significantly reducing memory demands. OpenMC achieves this through the Multipole Method, which analytically broadens cross-sections at runtime by using a mathematical multipole representation of resonances. In contrast, Serpent 2 applies a stochastic sampling approach: the velocity of each target nucleus is sampled from a Maxwellian distribution based on the material temperature, and the relative velocity between neutron and nucleus is used to determine the appropriate Doppler-broadened cross-section from the single reference dataset.

3. ANALYSIS

3.1. Mesh Generation

The benchmarking was performed on a mesh representing a single unit cell of an eVinci-like core, whose design was based on publicly available information found in the literature [8]. Figure 1 reports a schematic representation of the geometry, accompanied by some main design parameters. The eVinci-like microreactor is composed of a graphite block with holes for hosting sodium heat-pipes and the fuel rods. Fuel rods are made with TRISO particles embedded in a graphite matrix, with a packing factor of 40 %. For this study, only the active length of the unit cell was meshed, while the axial reflector was included in the Monte Carlo simulation through the built-in Constructive Solid Geometry method.

To maintain consistency in benchmarking and ensure correct mapping of fields, a single mesh was gen-

erated and subsequently converted into formats compatible with each code. Additionally, the application of the MOAB skinner within Cardinal required the mesh to be discretized entirely with tetrahedral elements, while this requirement does not exist in Serpent2. The use of a single mesh necessitated identifying an optimal compromise in mesh refinement: an excessively fine mesh can introduce significant statistical uncertainties in Monte Carlo tallies, whereas an overly coarse mesh may lead to numerical instabilities in the thermo-mechanical solution. OFFBEAT and Serpent2 require an OpenFOAM mesh format, which was created using the SALOME meshing software. This mesh was then converted using the MOAB library to the Exodus format, which is necessary for MOOSE. Since OpenMC performs Monte Carlo neutron transport simulations using DAGMC surface meshes, the mesh was converted from Exodus format using the DAGMC plugin provided by Coreform Cubit [9].

Aside from using the same conformal mesh across all codes, it was fundamental to ensure the same spatial accuracy for the thermal solver numerical solution. OFFBEAT is built upon the OpenFOAM framework, whose finite volume discretization schemes achieve up to second-order numerical accuracy. Therefore, MOOSE was configured to employ first-degree polynomial shape functions.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the unit cell.

3.2. Modeling

For the thermal problem, the heat pipes were modeled as ideal superconductors, a common assumption for these systems where heat removal is driven by the phase change of the working fluid, effectively resulting in isothermal behavior. The condenser-facing sides of the heat pipes were fixed at an operating temperature of 1073 K, while adiabatic boundary conditions were applied to all other external surfaces of the mesh. Temperature and irradiation-dependent models for graphite and fuel compact thermal conductivity were previously implemented in C. Genoni et al. [10] and integrated into the OFFBEAT material library. These models, taken from BISON documentation [11], were also incorporated into the MOOSE simulation. Their inclusion in MOOSE required no hard-coded implementation, but only input-level definitions. This was fundamental for ensuring that any observed differences in the results

could be attributed solely to solver or discretization effects, or, at most, to potential implementation discrepancies.

For the Monte Carlo models, although both Serpent2 and OpenMC are capable of explicitly modeling TRISO particles, this feature was not exploited in the present work. In the case of Serpent2, the use of an unstructured mesh to represent the geometry makes such an approach impractical: while Serpent2 includes a routine to generate a TRISO particle distribution within a given volume, applying it individually to each mesh cell would be impractical. On the other side, for OpenMC, the explicit TRISO modeling would dramatically increase the computational burden due to the surface-tracking routine required for neutron transport. As a result, a homogenization approach was adopted for the fuel compacts, assigning a uniform density based on the volume-weighted average of all the fuel components and the specified packing fraction. A similar homogenization strategy was applied to the heat pipes, where the density was uniformly smeared across the entire cross-section. The unit cell active length was represented using the mesh, while the axial reflectors were modeled via constructive solid geometry (CSG). Vacuum boundary conditions were applied at the axial boundaries, and periodic boundary conditions were applied at the radial boundaries. Both Monte Carlo simulations employed the ENDF/B-VII.1 nuclear data library. To achieve the same target uncertainty of 20 pcm in the multiplication factor, 20,000,000 particle histories were simulated in both codes. However, for tallying the power density, 100 times more particles were required by Serpent2 for reducing the statistical noise. This behavior is primarily due to the finer spatial discretization and the use of the delta-tracking neutron transport scheme, which restricts the calculation to collision-based tally estimators. In fact, these estimators are known to exhibit poorer statistical performance compared to track-length-based tallies, resulting in increased variance in the reported quantities.

3.3. Coupling

The coupling methodologies share a common foundation, relying on the exchange of key quantities between the thermo-mechanical solver and the Monte Carlo code, such as fission energy deposition, temperature, and density. For the Serpent2/OFFBEAT workflow, the multiphysics interface available in Serpent2 allows for the simulation of neutron transport directly on an OpenFOAM mesh, with material properties defined on a cell-by-cell basis. The fission energy deposition is tallied over the same mesh and passed to OFFBEAT for the thermo-mechanical analysis. OFFBEAT then solves for the temperature field and mesh displacement. Finally, the updated temperature distribution and deformed mesh can be used by Serpent2 to run an eigenvalue calculation and extract the temperature reactivity feedback. The process can be repeated till convergence. In contrast, Cardinal handles mesh deformation and field exchange between the two codes. Due to the surface neutron tracking routine in OpenMC, the MOAB skinner is required to dynamically generate tally regions during runtime. However, this approach comes at the expense of lower spatial resolution. It is important to note that although both simulation tools are capable of accounting for thermal deformation of the mesh, this study considered only thermal coupling—that is, only temperature and power deposition were exchanged between the two codes.

4. RESULTS

In the first part of the benchmarking, each thermal solver and Monte Carlo code was independently compared. For the thermal benchmark, a prescribed cosine-shaped power density distribution was applied. The parameters used for the code-to-code comparisons are summarized in Table I, and refer to the maximum and minimum temperatures in the fuel and the graphite block. Discrepancies within 5% were observed for these temperatures, which may be due to the different treatments used to account for temperature-dependent material properties. In fact, in OFFBEAT the thermal properties are implemented in the library as continuous analytical functions. On the other side, in MOOSE they are provided as tabulated data at 100 K temperature intervals, and piecewise linear interpolation

is performed automatically. For the Monte Carlo codes, an eigenvalue calculation was run, imposing a uniform temperature of 300 K for each material. The Serpent2 simulation yielded a multiplication factor of 1.14120 ± 0.00021 , while the OpenMC simulation gave 1.14230 ± 0.00021 , which is within the expected discrepancy.

Table I. Comparison between heat conduction and benchmark simulations in terms of maximum and minimum temperatures in the fuel and graphite.

	Fuel		Graphite	
	T_{\max}	T_{\min}	T_{\max}	T_{\min}
OFFBEAT	1405	1089	1360	1082
MOOSE	1401	1084	1330	1080

Table II. Comparison between serpent2 and OpenMC simulations in terms of k_{eff} .

	k_{eff}	
	Cold Uniform	Hot Non Uniform
Serpent2	1.14120 ± 0.00021	1.06096 ± 0.00021
OpenMC	1.14230 ± 0.00021	1.06128 ± 0.00022 – 10 temperature bins 1.06420 ± 0.00021 – 20 temperature bins

Figure 2. Power density distribution within the unit cell obtained by Cardinal using ten temperature bins (left) and by Serpent2 (right).

Figure 2 presents the power density distributions tallied by Serpent2 and Cardinal. With only 10 temperature bins, the mesh cells generated by the MOAB skinner in Cardinal lack sufficient spatial resolution to accurately capture the localized power density peaks at the fuel rod ends. In Cardinal, doubling the number of bins from 1500 to 3500 improves the spatial resolution but increases the computational cost, with the total CPU time rising from 280 to 440 CPU-hours. Serpent2 allows to tally over the full 500,000 cells with similar computational resources. However, for a fair comparison in terms of computational effort, an optimal balance between spatial resolution and run time should ideally be identified through a sensitivity analysis in both codes. This would allow to determine the resolution beyond which no significant change in the multiplication factor is observed or the one with negligible statistical

Figure 3. Temperature distribution (left), temperature bins (center), and power density (right) obtained by Cardinal.

oscillations in the tallied quantities. However, such an analysis lies outside the scope of the present study

Table II compares the resulting multiplication factors under hot operating conditions with the non-uniform temperature distribution from the thermal solver. Both Serpent2/OFFBEAT and Cardinal exhibit negative reactivity feedback of approximately 8000 pcm from Doppler broadening. Furthermore, the multiplication factor results obtained by Cardinal across varying numbers of temperature bins reveal some dependency on the spatial mesh resolution. This suggests that Cardinal may require a dedicated sensitivity analysis to determine the optimal number of temperature bins, beyond which the dependency on bin resolution becomes negligible.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This preliminary benchmark compares the Serpent2/OFFBEAT workflow against Cardinal. The benchmark is performed on a radially infinite lattice of an eVinci-like microreactor.

The two workflows share a common structure: neutron transport is first simulated using Monte Carlo methods on an unstructured mesh representing the unit cell. These tallied power density results are transferred to the thermo-mechanical solver to calculate temperature and displacement fields. In subsequent iterations, neutron transport can be re-simulated on the updated mesh, with cross-sections updated according to the computed temperature distribution.

Before comparing the capabilities of the full coupling, the results of the two solvers and the two Monte Carlo Codes were compared. With a cosine power density distribution imposed, the thermal solvers demonstrated excellent agreement, with discrepancies in the maximum and minimum fuel and graphite temperatures of approximately 5%. For the Monte Carlo codes, the multiplication factor was compared under uniform temperature conditions. The resulting multiplication factors differed by roughly 100 pcm between Serpent2 and OpenMC. Finally, the thermal coupling routines were benchmarked, and both codes produced negative temperature reactivity feedback of approximately 8000 pcm. Such an effect seemed to be quite sensitive to the number of temperature bins used in Cardinal to dynamically generate cells for the Monte Carlo simulation.

Since the standalone thermal and neutronic simulations agreed closely, the remaining differences in

coupled-feedback results and computational effort are attributable primarily to the different neutron tracking routines and spatial resolution. The Serpent2/OFFBEAT workflow was able to run with comparable computational resources with respect to Cardinal, but with almost 150 times more cells thanks to the delta neutron tracking routine. However, it should be emphasized that this level of spatial resolution may not be strictly necessary for the system under investigation. Its adequacy can only be established through a dedicated sensitivity analysis aimed at identifying the optimal spatial discretization.

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